

WAYS TO IMPROVE MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING THE PRINCIPLES OF INSTITUTIONAL INDEPENDENCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS ON THE BASIS OF INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

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Abstract: In this article, the theoretical and methodological foundations of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence, the ways of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence based on international standards, the tasks of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence are studied. Also, current issues of improving the mechanisms of introducing the principles of institutional independence are analyzed.

Key words: institutional independence, principle, mechanism, improvement, theoretical-methodological basis, international standards, management, managerial competencies, academic, educational determinants, marketing, management, integration, forecasting, globalization, functional, digitized system.

INTRODUCTION.

At present, the autonomy gained by universities is primarily reflected in the ability to independently develop curricula and programs, define the content and methods of teaching, and create new elective courses. Universities have achieved independence in their financial and economic activities. Today, universities have the authority to choose their organizational structure, form student contingents, and select ways to raise funds through various educational, scientific, and other activities. The implementation of an autonomous approach to higher education requires an understanding of the ideas of independence in education in the context of the educational environment of universities. Addressing this issue involves taking into account several factors that affect the effectiveness of the processes being studied.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS.

The methodological aspects of implementing the principles of institutional independence have been studied and analyzed in the scientific works of scholars from our country, such as U.SH. Begimkulov, B.SH. Usmanov, M.F. Hakimova, M.A. Yuldashev, Z.K. Ismailova, Q.X. Abdurakhmanov, G.N. Akhunova, B.A. Begalov, A.SH. Bekmurodov, S.S. Gulyamov, Sh.N. Zaynutdinov, M.A. Ikramov,

N.K. Yo'ldoshev, I.U. Majidov, D.X. Nabiyeu, R.I. Nurimbetov, B.X. Rakhimov, D.N. Rakhimova, R.A. Rakhmanbayeva, M.X. Saidov, A.N. Samadov, T.SH. Shodiyev, Sh.D. Ergashkhodzhayeva, A.T. Yusupov, Sh. Qurbonov, and others, as well as scholars from the CIS countries, including N.V. Demidov, S.V. Sulima, S.A. Druzhilov, K.I. Morozova, S.D. Reznik, S.M. Vasin, O.A. Sazikina, O. Bichkova, L. Verbitskaya, V. Kasevich, M.V. Niyazova, V.YE. Varavenko, Johan G. Vissema, F. Altbach, P.Y. Grishina, R.N. Abramov, E.V. Galajinskiy, A.O. Grudzinskiy, R. Dim, V. Konnov, M. Repina, and others.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION.

The large scale and new quality of educational and professional tasks require new competencies from both students and teachers. From this perspective, one of the significant results of modern higher education is the acquisition of other competencies, accelerated development, and improvement of the quality of service, which, in turn, should play a leading role in professional and personal self-development through metasubject (or universal) competencies. In general, implementing an autonomous approach requires a restructuring of the thinking of all participants in the educational environment of the university (administrative staff, faculty members, students, service staff), and they must be prepared to accept increased responsibility.

When discussing the risks that arise in this context, it is important to understand deeply that the autonomy in education should not be perceived merely as "freedom" from management but as a balance between freedom and responsibility, with a focus on creativity and constant personal and professional self-development. Without a profound understanding of the ideals of individual independence in education, the intrinsic characteristics of an autonomous individual, such as independence, confidence, and initiative, may end up overshadowing virtues like respect and ethics that are characteristic of a well-educated person. Examples of negative manifestations of auto-innovation under the condition of freedom include resistance to change, loss of control over one's activities, and similar issues.

Favorable socio-cultural factors create the basis for the development of institutional independence, while academic factors, in turn, create the necessary conditions for its manifestation and development in the university's educational environment. Ultimately, personal factors determine the level of autonomy that participants in the educational process "internalize." Finally, autonomous subjects can positively influence the social and cultural environment of

educational innovations and establish the most crucial conditions for their implementation.

From a practical point of view, in the educational environment, there are social-cultural, academic, and personal factors that can have both positive and negative effects on the provision of institutional independence to universities, as well as on the formation and development of independence.

It is undeniable that the political, economic, and social well-being of any country is closely linked to the development level of its education system. Education is a social institution that develops and efficiently gathers human capital, shapes a person's socially significant ideals and worldview positions, and determines the future of both society and the individual. It is now seen not only as a mechanism for transferring and mastering theoretical and methodological knowledge, skills, and competencies but also as a process aimed at shaping a socially and professionally active person with high skills, mobility, adaptability, independence, and expertise.

Institutional independence allows teachers to present the subject according to their own preferences, choose the topic and methodology for research, and grants certain rights to teachers (professors, researchers) and students, allowing them to acquire knowledge based on their inclinations and needs.

The institutional independence of students helps in the formation of personal qualities and abilities during the professional preparation process, ensuring that the educational system's task of preparing competitive individuals, who meet the demands of the labor market, is fulfilled.

When students are provided minimal opportunities to participate in shaping their educational content, the process of organizing elective courses, which would allow them to exercise this right, becomes even more diminished. One of the flaws of the system is that when selecting courses for development within departments, students' academic interests are not considered. However, students often face the reality of having to choose one of 2-3 already developed academic subjects. As a core component of the curriculum, elective courses should be structured annually based on students' educational needs, with students being the "clients" of those courses. If this mechanism does not work effectively, it leads to a decrease in the efficiency of tasks handled by elective courses:

- Giving students the right to participate in shaping their educational content, in accordance with legal regulations;

- Providing students with independence and the opportunity to satisfy their creative inquiries, while also managing the quality of specialist training through substantiated and methodologically appropriate recommendations.

All of this creates a situation where elective courses are evaluated as less important and secondary in the teaching process for both teachers and students.

In strategic planning of the education service market, the analysis of the competitive environment can be grouped based on M. Porter's competitive strategy concept:

- First group consists of producers of similar products, which reflects the internal competition within higher education institutions specializing in a specific field of education.

- Second group consists of suppliers of raw materials, materials, and semi-finished products. In the education service market, this group includes teaching materials, the institution's technical equipment, and teaching staff.

- Third group includes the product buyers, who are students themselves.

- Fourth group consists of entities capable of producing similar products.

- Fifth group includes substitutes for product producers. In the education service market, an example of this would be a higher education institution that prepares students in a different field but also offers an economics program, which can attract potential students interested in the economics field.

According to the approach of Philip Kotler, higher education marketing involves developing, analyzing, planning, implementing, and controlling well-defined programs to facilitate the exchange of values in targeted education service markets.

In the education service market, the seller helps display and shape the market supply. The seller should possess specialized knowledge and be able to present it to consumers based on their needs.

CONCLUSION.

In the educational process, freedom of choice remains one of the most important factors that help increase students' engagement in the professional preparation process. It allows students to make choices, set goals, and implement them through analysis, reflection, and self-assessment, thereby fostering subjectivity, organicity, integrity, and responsibility. Institutional independence is particularly relevant in the preparation of pedagogical staff capable of effectively fulfilling their professional duties in the context of the changing socio-pedagogical environment in our country.

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